

EVALUATION OF POST-CONSUMER RECYCLED POLYPROPYLENE-BASED COMPOSITE MATERIALS REINFORCED WITH RICE HUSK FIBERS

Juan Porras¹, Maria A. Morales¹, Alejandro Maranon², Camilo Hernandez³, Véronique Michaud⁴, and Alicia Porras¹

1. Products and Processes Design Group (GDPP), Department of Chemical and Food Engineering, Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia

2. Structural Integrity Research Group, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia

3. Sustainable Design in Mechanical Engineering Research Group (DSIM), Mechanical Engineering, Escuela Colombiana de Ingeniería Julio Garavito, Bogotá, Colombia

4. Laboratory for Processing for Advanced Composites (LPAC), Institute of Materials (IMX), École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Lausanne, Switzerland

INTRODUCTION

The Circular Economy is a consumption model based on intelligent waste management, which has been steadily growing over the last two decades. The use and management of agro-industrial waste is an integral part of the generation of closed-cycle materials that support the pillars of a society based on sustainable development [1]. One of the most produced agro-industrial waste in the world is rice husk (RH) with about 180 million ton/year [1]. It is a by-product limited mainly to energy generation by burning, but it could instead find applications in composite materials [2].

On the other hand, although plastic consumption has increased worldwide, recycling rates are often not higher than 5% in many countries including the United States [3]. Therefore, the development of novel products based on recycled plastics, such as post-consumer polypropylene (rPP), and RH fibers becomes a great alternative to contribute to waste reduction and the adoption of a circular economy model.

The present work aims to evaluate the potential of RH-based fibers implementation as fillers in composites based on post-consumer recycled polypropylene. A design of experiments was used to study the influence of the type of filler (Untreated rice husk – RH and isolated cellulose extracted from rice husk – RHC) and the use of coupling agent (with and without polypropylene-grafted-maleic anhydride – MAPP) on mechanical, physical, and thermal properties of the recycled polypropylene biocomposites.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Materials

2. Experimental design

3. Manufacturing

4. Characterization methods

Thermal characterization

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA):

- ASTM E1131
- Ramp: 10°C/min at 100 mL/min nitrogen flow rate

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC):

- ASTM D3418
- Ramp: 5°C/min at 400 mL/min nitrogen flow rate

Mechanical characterization

Tensile test:

- ASTM D790 (5 specimens)
- Universal Machine Instron 3367
- Load Cell: 30 kN
- Crosshead Speed: 5 mm/min

Izod impact test:

- ASTM D256 (5 unnotched specimens)
- TMI 43-1 impact machine
- 2.7J max. impact energy pendulum

RESULTS

TGA

Fig. 1. (a) TGA and (b) DTGA for rPP and rPP-based composites reinforced-infill with RH and RHC.

- ➔ 250 – 350°C: mainly lignocellulosic RH and RHC (6%).
- ➔ 350 – 500°C: Mainly degradation of rPP.
- ➔ Composites residues (fiber ash at 600°C): 1 - 5%.
- ➔ RHC produces lower residues than RH.
- ➔ The degradation process of the composites started in a similar temperature range as the neat rPP due to the low fiber and additive (MAPP) fractions.

DSC

Fig. 2. (a) DSC crystallization and (b) melting for rPP and rPP-based composites.

Table 1. Temperatures and enthalpies of melting and crystallization of rPP and composites.

Formulation	Tc (°C)	ΔHc (J/g)	Tm (°C)	ΔHm (J/g)	% Crystallinity
rPP	132,72 ± 0,82	98,38 ± 0,74	168,44 ± 0,35	84,23 ± 0,45	40,69 ± 0,22
rPP-RH	133,17 ± 0,77	91,16 ± 2,32	168,03 ± 0,16	76,45 ± 0,81	36,93 ± 0,39
rPP-RHC	133,33 ± 0,73	89,24 ± 1,82	168,04 ± 0,28	77,58 ± 2,05	37,48 ± 0,99
rPP-RH-MAPP	130,12 ± 0,50	79,41 ± 6,56	167,24 ± 0,14	78,29 ± 2,70	37,82 ± 1,30
rPP-RHC-MAPP	130,81 ± 0,18	84,39 ± 6,04	167,65 ± 0,12	80,42 ± 0,27	38,85 ± 0,13

- ➔ All the materials have a melting temperature of 167-169°C and a crystallization point above 130°C.
- ➔ The composite's crystallinity (36-38%) is lower than the matrix (~41%) because the MAPP and reinforcement incorporation inhibit early nucleation, thus reducing crystallinity.

Mechanical performance

Table 2. Mechanical properties of rPP-based materials.

Formulation	Tensile strength [MPa]	Young's modulus [GPa]	Tensile strain at maximum load [%]	Impact strength [kJ m ⁻²]
rPP	32.06 ± 0.18	2.19 ± 0.05	4.96 ± 0.27	18.28 ± 1.89
rPP-RH	27.11 ± 0.56	2.40 ± 0.07	3.36 ± 0.10	8.77 ± 0.86
rPP-RHC	27.10 ± 0.41	2.73 ± 0.07	2.64 ± 0.11	7.61 ± 0.78
rPP-RH-MAPP	31.97 ± 0.16	2.55 ± 0.05	3.05 ± 0.14	9.89 ± 1.34
rPP-RHC-MAPP	32.17 ± 0.62	2.33 ± 0.06	3.92 ± 0.11	15.06 ± 1.49

Fig. 3. (a) Tensile stress-strain curve and (b) impact strength for rPP and composites.

- ➔ The impact strength of the rPP-RHC-MAPP formulation is only 17.6% lower than that of the neat rPP. The other formulations show lower values between 46 and 58%.
- ➔ In rPP-RH-MAPP and rPP-RHC-MAPP composites, tensile strength is not significantly different from neat rPP, and Young's modulus is improved by 16.43% and 6.39%, respectively. rPP-RH and rPP-RHC (MAPP-free composites) also increased Young's modulus by 9.5% and 24.7%, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

Composites based on post-consumer polypropylene filled with rice husk were produced using compression molding. The mechanical and thermal properties of the improved formulation (rPP-RHC-MAPP) showed the great potential of rice husk as a filler for post-consumer recycled polypropylene composites. The results also show the importance of adding a coupling agent between natural fibers and a hydrophobic matrix. Finally, this study illustrates an opportunity to generate added value for agro-industrial waste and recycled polymers by developing sustainable, eco-friendly products that contribute to a circular economy.

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CONTACT INFORMATION

J.P. js.porras@uniandes.edu.co
A.P. n-porras@uniandes.edu.co
Bogotá, Colombia